

Equity in the Nigerian Education Sector: Problems and Opportunities

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“It is not beyond our power to create a world in which all children have access to good education” – Nelson Mandela.

It was the year 2014. Over 500 school girls, nestled in their school’s boarding facilities, prepared for their final secondary school exams after years of hard work to obtain quality education in a region where less than 1 in 5 women completed secondary school.¹ However, their dreams were dashed by terrorists who kidnapped and later abused or killed 219 of them, also known as the Chibok Girls.²

The Chibok Girls’ story is a stark reminder of the existing inequities experienced by women and girls in the country’s education sector. Equity in education means that “personal or social circumstances, such as gender, are not obstacles to achieving educational potential.”³ Women and girls ought to have equal access to quality education as it is a constitutionally guaranteed right⁴; however, this remains a mirage.

Statistics by the United Nations Children’s Fund (UNICEF) reveal that about 10 million girls – 60% of the total number of out-of-school children – have never seen

¹ Enyioko, Newman (2021). Gender Equality and Educational System in Nigeria. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=3825028> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3825028> . (Accessed 23 March 2023).

² BBC, *Nigeria Chibok Abductions: What we know.* (8 May 2017). Available at <https://www.bbc.com/news/world-africa-32299943.amp> accessed 23 March 2023.

³ Asian Society, *Equity and Quality in Education.* (N.D.) Available at: [https://asiasociety.org/education/equity-and-quality-education#:~:text=Equity%20in%20education%20means%20that,skills%20\(definition%20of%20inclusion\)](https://asiasociety.org/education/equity-and-quality-education#:~:text=Equity%20in%20education%20means%20that,skills%20(definition%20of%20inclusion)) accessed 25 March 2023.

⁴ Section 18, Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria 1999 (as amended)

the four walls of a classroom.⁵ Literacy rates for women across the country is just above 50%; almost twenty percentage points less than their male counterparts. Women are also left behind in university enrolment, as only 43.1% of women as against 56.9% of men obtained admission into Nigerian universities as at 2017.⁶ Inequities still persist in academic faculties as just over 15% of Nigeria's professors are women.⁷

To fully embrace equity in education, in line with the International Women's Day 2023 theme, we need to apply Simon Sinek's methodology of solving challenges by "starting with why". Only by understanding the nature of the problem can we find possible opportunities to make education fully inclusive and accessible to all.

The Problem of Inequity in Nigeria's Educational Sector

The issue of inequity in Nigeria's education sector is a complex cocktail of challenges such as Nigeria's patriarchal culture and cultural practices, prevailing socioeconomic conditions, exacerbating insecurity, and limited facilities for quality learning.

The dominant patriarchal beliefs regard women and girls as socially inferior to men and relegate them to the domestic functions; that is, women are often seen as "belonging to the kitchen and the other room." Educating girls is therefore believed to be counterproductive since women are judged to have little or no economic contributions. Again, child marriage is still commonly practiced in line with these beliefs and 43% of girls in Nigeria are married off before they turn eighteen,

⁵ Opara, Ijeoma (2022). Over 10 Million Girls are Out of School – UNICEF. *International Centre for Investigative Reporting*. Available at: <https://www.icirigeria.org/over-10-million-girls-out-of-school-in-nigeria-unicef/> (Accessed 23 March 2023).

⁶ Country Economy (2018). Nigeria's Literacy Rate. Available at: <https://countryeconomy.com/demography/literacy-rate/nigeria> (Accessed 23 March 2023).

⁷ Enyioko, Newman (ibid N.I), <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.3825028>

effectively hindering their possibilities of furthering their education.⁸ Moreover, these same patriarchal cultural attitudes prevent women from breaking the glass ceiling in their careers when they work as teachers and lecturers.

Poverty is another major obstacle, with over 60% of the country's residents classified as multidimensional poor in 2022.⁹ While basic education is officially free, in reality, many publicly-owned schools are either too dilapidated, too distant, or otherwise inaccessible for many low-income families. Moreover, the related epidemic of child labour means that many families send their girl children to the streets or to the homes of the more affluent to work full-time.

With the increasing attacks of terrorists on schools and the general unrest caused by the activities of bandits, kidnappers, and other criminals, the education of many girls have been truncated as they are more vulnerable.¹⁰ The abysmal state of educational facilities in most parts of the country, poor standards of teaching, and lack of hygiene amenities – which is especially important for female students who have monthly period cycles – also compounds the challenge.

Opportunities to Embrace Equity in Nigeria's Education Sector

Between 2003 and 2018, female literacy rates rose by about 10 percentage points.¹¹ This demonstrates that despite the multifaceted nature of the problems preventing the education sector from being equitable for women and girls, Nigeria has the

⁸ Borgen Project (2017). The Five Main Barriers to Providing Girls Education in Nigeria. Available at: <https://www.borgenmagazine.com/barriers-to-girls-education-in-nigeria/> (Accessed 23 March 2023)

⁹ National Bureau of Statistics (2022). Nigeria Launches its most Extensive Measure of Multidimensional Poverty. Available at: <https://nigerianstat.gov.ng/news/78#:~:text=Highlights%20of%20the%202022%20Multidimensional,quarter%20of%20all%20possible%20deprivations.> (Accessed 23 March 2023).

¹⁰ Nawrozzada, Selman (2020). Girls Education in Nigeria. *Centre for African Justice*. Available at: <https://centreforafricanjustice.org/girls-education-in-nigeria/> (Accessed 23 March 2023).

¹¹ Ibid, n. VI . <https://countryeconomy.com/demography/literacy-rate/nigeria>

capacity to create the suitable environment for equitable education to thrive. That can be achieved by maximising these opportunities:

1. Embracing equity from the classrooms:

This means that the educational system at all levels – from policy and governance, to curricula, pedagogy, and learning environments – should mainstream gender equity. There should be fairness and representation in the appointment of school administrators, professors, and teachers; school-children should be reoriented to eschew harmful patriarchal beliefs about the female gender; and safe and healthy learning environments should be provided.

2. Equitable financing:

Equitable financing also holds the key to encourage quality education for all in Nigeria. According to the UNICEF in its 2022 “*Transforming Education with Equitable Financing*” report, bridging the huge educational finance gap in African countries like Nigeria would be able to support not only foundational learning for the most marginalised – including girls – but will also provide aid for women and girls from disadvantaged backgrounds to further their education.¹² Therefore, the federal and state governments must increase their budgetary allocations for education and partner with private entities to raise funds for education where possible.

3. Unlocking digital innovation:

The COVID-19 pandemic enabled the world to unlock innovative pathways for delivering education through digital technology. Nigeria is well-positioned to maximise this opportunity to ensure equitable access to learning as it has the highest rate of digital penetration in Sub-Saharan Africa.¹³ Both the government and technology innovators should thus make collaborative efforts towards deploying

¹² UNICEF (2022). *Transforming Education with Equitable Financing*, pp. 2. Available at: <https://www.unicef.org/reports/transforming-education-equitable-financing> . (Accessed 25 March, 2023.)

¹³ Data Reportal (2023). *Digital 2023: Nigeria*. Available at: <https://datareportal.com/reports/digital-2023-nigeria>. (Accessed 25 March 2023).

Ed-tech solutions to reach even the most marginalised communities with learning resources.

Conclusion

The problem of inequity affecting our education sector is a huge drawback to the country's socio-economic development. Studies have shown that when women and girls have equitable access to education, poverty rates dramatically fall, less young people are unemployed, maternal and neonatal mortality significantly reduces, and economies experience sporadic growth.¹⁴ Thus, if Nigeria is to witness the transformative development it has sought for so long, we must begin by prioritising equitable opportunities for women and girls to learn and to teach.

¹⁴ UNICEF (2023). Girls Education. Available at: <https://www.unicef.org/education/girls-education> (Accessed 23 March 2023).